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POSTER PRESENTATIONS

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USE OF CONTINUOUS PASSIVE MOVEMENT IN CHILDREN'S REHABILITATION – CASE REPORT

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Introduction: Performing continuous passive movement (CPM) enables early injured limb mobilization, which is limited during active movement by the activation of injured muscles and surrounding structures, thus increasing pain intensity. Robotic devices such as the ARTROMOT® E2-E2 compact device are used for this purpose in rehabilitation treatment. Artromot is a motorized device for CPM that ensures the performance of all elbow joint movements. The aim of our work is to show the results achieved after seven-day Artromot-assisted therapy in a patient who, as a result of a humerus fracture, had a contracture, reduced hand grip strength and pain in the injured arm.

Materials and methods: An 8-year-old male was treated at the Clinic for a supracondylar fracture of the left humerus, which is non-dominant arm. At the intake, after conservative treatment of the fracture, elbow joint mobility and hand grip strength were measured with a goniometer and a dynamometer, respectively, and the pain intensity was evaluated using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS, 0–100 mm) and the Wong Baker Scale (0–10). After seven days of CPM therapy with the Artromot device, the same evaluations were repeated.

Results: After Artromot-assisted therapy, significant improvements in elbow joint mobility, as well as an increase in the hand grip strength were noted, while pain intensity declined (Table 1).

Table 1. Functional parameters in the injured arm before and after therapy

	Flexion (degree)	Extension (degree)	Dynamometer (J/kg)	VAS scale (mm)	Wong Baker scale
Before	110	-30	3	30	3.6
After	135	-5	7	18	1.4

Conclusion:

Use of robotic devices in pediatric rehabilitation contributes to better outcomes and should be considered as an aid in the process of acquiring better functionality of the injured limb.

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Keywords: elbow; pediatric rehabilitation; Artromot; continuous passive motion